

ISic0169

I.Sicily inscription 0169

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Tuuli Ahlholm,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Thermae Himeraeae

Place of origin (modern)

Termini Imerese

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Palermo, Museo Archeologico

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. [.] Domitius A(uli) · f(ilius) · Quir(ina) · Himeraeus

2. sibi · et · Domitiae A(uli) · f(iliae) · sorori

3. [e]t · Alfae · □ · l(ibertae) · Zoticae · uxori

Apparatus

Text based on ILTermini, with slight amendments.

Translation (en)

...Domitius Himeraeus, son of Aulus, of the Quirina tribe, (erected this) for himself and for his sister Domitia, daughter of Aulus, and for Alfia, (soon to be?) his freedwoman, and Zotica, his wife.

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 285244

EDR 111313

EDCS 22100099

Bibliography

Mommsen, Th. 1883. Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. *Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum, consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae editum*. Berlin. At 10.7398 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/item/buchseite/650798>)

Bivona, L. 1970. Iscrizioni latine lapidarie del Museo di Palermo. *Sikelia*. Palermo. At 77

Bivona, L. 1994. Iscrizioni latine lapidarie del museo civico di Termini Imerese. *Kokalos Supplementi / Sikelika serie storica*. Palermo / Rome. At 90

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